

ISic0802

Latin fragment mentioning a basilica

Language

Latin

Type

honorific(?)

Material

marble

Object

tabula

Editor

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Autopsy

2011-06-15

Last Change

2019-07-25 - Jonathan Prag revised the file further from autopsy and fresh images

Place of origin (ancient)

Halaesa

Place of origin (modern)

near Castel di Tusa

Provenance

Excavated 9 September 1970, on the pavement of the west portico of the agora, in front of room 2

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Halaesa, Antiquarium e sito archeologico di Halaesa, inventory ME 20225

Physical Description

Two joining fragments of a slab of white marble, broken on all sides, finished smooth on the reverse

Dimensions

Height 21.8 cm

Width 22.5 cm

Depth 1.5 cm

Layout

Parts of three lines of Latin letters are preserved

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are neatly V-cut and well-proportioned, with modest serifs. Neither lines 1 nor 3 are completely preserved, but line 1 is taller than line 2, and line 3 is shorter

Letter heights:

Line 2: 70 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]equo[---]

2. [---]basiliç[a][---]

3. [---]operi[bus][---]

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Editors from Scibona onwards have suggested reading *equo publico* in line 1, a mark of rank and distinction. The honorand's name would presumably have stood first in the upper, now lost, part of the text, and other indications of rank and office-holding, potentially both imperial and municipal, would have followed, together with *equo publico*. Line 2 must be a reference to a basilica, which suggests that the text recorded building work / euergetism undertaken by the honorand. Scibona suggested that the letters in line 3 formed part of a name, but Manganaro's reading of *operi[bus]* is better, and accords well with the visible traces (cf. Prestianni Giallombardo 2012 n.100) and so line 3 is likely to make further reference to the works undertaken by the honorand.

The reference to a basilica is significant. Text no.35, also from the agora, also records a basilica, and the bronzes honouring Nemenios (no.60) include the option that the statue of Nemenios be erected 'in the basilica'. The Nemenios bronzes take reference to this building back to the first century BC. Text no.35 is of monumental scale and may belong to the act of (re)building to which this inscription appears to make reference. There continues to be debate over whether the term is intended to designate, or originally evolved to designate, primarily building form or simply function. Buildings termed 'basilica', especially in the Republican period, have considerable variety of form; but they also have considerable variety of use (see Gros 1996: 238-55). As David has noted, *basilicae* served a judicial role alongside others, hosting the tribunals of Roman officials (David 1983: 219-28). Cicero's Verrines attest to the use of porticoes in the agorai of the cities of Sicily by Verres and his subordinates for the administration of provincial government (Cic. Verr. 3.77, 4.85-6), and it is therefore very likely that the building called the basilica at Halaesa is part or the whole of the porticoed building standing on the agora (cf. Scibona 2009b: 27 n.64, 42-43), and that this text refers to an act of repair or rebuilding in the imperial period.

Digital identifiers:

TM 175720

EDR 075542

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